

Thank you for taking the time to provide detailed feedback on our Data Management Plan (DMP). We appreciate your constructive comments, which have helped us improve the quality and clarity of our plan. In response to your suggestions, we have made several changes and clarifications. Please find a summary of these modifications below:

We have updated section 3.1.1.3 to indicate that we will be using standardized vocabularies and controlled vocabularies for metadata description, improving the overall consistency and interoperability of our dataset. We chose to adopt DataCite schema: “A set of mandatory metadata that must be registered with the DataCite Metadata Store when minting a DOI persistent identifier for a dataset. The domain-agnostic properties were chosen for their ability to aid in accurate and consistent identification of data for citation and retrieval purposes.

Sponsored by the DataCite consortium, version 3.0 was recently released in 2013.”

In sections 3.1.1.7 and 3.1.1.8, we have addressed the issue of naming conventions by incorporating the use of self-defined naming conventions for files and data entities, which will provide a consistent and clear structure for our dataset. The conventions are described [here](#).

For section 3.1.1.9, we have removed the "if necessary" expression and decided to adopt [Semantic Versioning](#) guidelines.

In response to the comment regarding section 1.1.3, we have clarified that the format of the described generated/collected data is Python software, as it can be considered indeed a type of data. We have also made it clear that our software is written in Python programming language, hence .py is our data format.

We have thoroughly proofread the DMP to correct grammatical errors and ensure clarity throughout the document.

Once again, we thank you for your valuable feedback, which has significantly contributed to the improvement of our Data Management Plan. We hope that the changes made address your concerns and suggestions effectively. Please do not hesitate to contact us if you have any further questions or require additional clarification.